

DEVELOPING LEARNERS' SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING ABILITY THROUGH DIGITAL TOOLS: FOCUSING ON CLASSROOM PRACTICES

LEE JIYOUN

Senior Lecturer, Department of Foreign Languages, Samarkand Branch of KIUT

E-mail: yalin412@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17651123>

ABSTRACT

Since the COVID-19 pandemic, learning through digital devices has spread rapidly and become a normalized and inevitable phenomenon. This trend is equally evident in foreign language education.

This paper explores how self-directed learning can be realized in Korean classical literature and K-pop culture classes using digital tools and examines the prerequisites for developing learners' self-directed learning ability. In addition, it proposes ways to enhance self-directed learning skills by suggesting what educational institutions, local governments, and students themselves can do to foster continuous learning ability and sustainable educational development in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: digital tools, self-directed learning, Korean language education, digital literacy, learning ability development

INTRODUCTION

With globalization and the worldwide popularity of Korean culture, Korean language and cultural education are being conducted through various approaches. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, education utilizing diverse digital devices has rapidly expanded and become the norm. Such tools are widely employed to facilitate self-directed learning, and related research has become increasingly active. Accordingly, this study examines how learners' self-directed learning abilities can be developed through digital tools in Korean language education, based on actual classroom examples.

MAIN DISCUSSION

Self-directed learning using digital tools refers to a learning method in which the learner independently manages the entire process—from deciding whether to engage in learning, to setting appropriate goals, establishing strategies to achieve them, and evaluating outcomes (Knowles, 1975:18).

Relevant prior research includes Park Young-ju (2025), who explored the effects of ChatGPT use on self-directed learning ability and Korean writing skills among foreign learners of Korean.

According to Hobbs (2010:17), digital media literacy encompasses the use of text, tools, and technology, as well as critical analysis, creative production, and ethical thinking. Studies related to digital literacy include Ahn Mi-ae (2024).

Learning and appreciating Korean classical literature is also one of many methods of Korean language education.

Photo 1 and 2 show a classroom activity in which students studied Eobusasisa (The Fisherman’s Four Seasons Song) by the classical Korean poet Yoon Seon-do and visualized their impressions of the poem through drawings. Since Eobusasisa was written in the Joseon period, it is difficult for students to fully grasp the nuances of Middle Korean or the sentiments of the era. Thus, after listening to **the instructor’s** explanation, students used their mobile phones to search for additional materials independently, then drew images reflecting their personal interpretations. They also referred to AI-recommended images as visual aids.

Classroom Photos from Korean Classical Literature and K-pop Culture Lessons		
Photo1	Photo2	Photo3

As demonstrated in this example, if learners in various foreign language classes listen to the instructor’s overview and then use digital devices to autonomously gather supplementary materials before visualizing their understanding, the learning process can become significantly more effective. This approach aligns with the findings of prior studies.

A prerequisite for self-directed learning through digital tools is digital literacy. Many people use smartphones for foreign language learning—for vocabulary acquisition or multistep learning using automatically translated sentences. However, if learners cannot discern which resources or applications are most suitable or whether machine translations contain errors, even the best digital tools will not guarantee effective self-directed learning. This point is also highlighted by Kim Ji-hye (2025).

Photo 3 shows a classroom scene from a K-pop culture lesson, in which differences in digital literacy among students influenced the quality and quantity of learning outcomes. To address this, students first worked in pairs before engaging

in group discussions. Each pair consisted of one learner with higher digital literacy and one with lower skills. They translated and wrote down K-pop lyrics into Uzbek. Each student looked up the meanings of assigned words using smartphones and collaboratively compiled a vocabulary list. During this process, learners with weaker digital literacy learned efficient device use from their partners. Since translation errors in digital tools can lead to learning errors, verification was conducted during the group activity.

As a result, students with lower digital literacy improved their skills by learning from peers. During the group verification stage, they shared Uzbek meanings and cross-checked potential errors collaboratively. This activity exemplifies the progression from pair work to jigsaw activities, which are typical in foreign language education. Furthermore, the findings show notable parallels with studies by Lim Hee-ju and Cha Min-young (2024) and by Park Young-ju (2025), which investigated self-directed learning through ChatGPT use.

CONCLUSION & SUGGESTIONS

As shown in the above cases, using digital tools can enhance not only learners' digital literacy but also their self-directed learning ability. Moreover, it can transform the entire class into an autonomous learning community that grows collaboratively. A limitation of this study is the lack of quantitative data verifying the effectiveness of developing self-directed learning skills through digital tools in Korean classical literature classes, which should be addressed in future research.

In modern society, learning with digital tools has already become an unavoidable reality. Self-directed learning is essential for improving individuals' lifelong learning capacity and for the sustainable development of education in Uzbekistan. Therefore, this paper suggests continuous support from educational institutions and local governments to improve digital literacy and emphasizes the importance of students' own motivation and effort to enhance their digital competence.

REFERENCES

1. Kim, Nara. (2022). A Study on the Composition of Korean Language Courses to Strengthen Digital Literacy Capability. *Bilingual Research*, 89, 1–25.
2. Kim, Ji-hye. (2025). A Survey on the Perception and Usage of Korean Language Learners for Academic Purposes on Generative AI: A Case Study of University A. *The Journal of Humanities*, 46, 13–43.
3. Park, Young-ju. (2025). The Effects of ChatGPT Use on Self-Directed Learning Ability and Korean Writing Skills of Foreign Learners of Korean as a Second Foreign Language. *The Journal of the Korea Contents Association*, 25(10), 565–577.
4. Seo, Yu-yeon. (2023). The Effect of Korean Language Learners' Perception of

- Educational Service Quality on the Formation of Self-Directed Learning Ability. *Journal of Korean Language Education*, 34(4), 187–210.
5. Ahn, Mi-ae. (2024). Exploring the Applications and Methodologies of Digital Literacy in Korean Linguistics Research. *Eomun Nonjip*, 100, 125–151.
 6. Lim, Hee-ju & Cha, Min-young. (2024). The Effects of Online Reading Strategies on English Writing Strategies – The Mediating Effects of ChatGPT. *Culture and Convergence*, 46(Special Issue 1), 529–537.
 7. Hobbs, R. (2010). Digital and Media Literacy: A Plan of Action. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3rWVbft>
 8. Knowles, M. (1975). *Self-Directed Learning: A Guide for Learners and Teachers*. Follett Publishing Company.